

EVALUATION OF LEARNING OBJECTS COMPATIBLE WITH MOBILE DEVICES IN BIOLOGY TEACHING

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5635398

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ABSTRACT

Learning objects are digital resources used in teaching. However, these objects are little used by teachers, due to the lack of knowledge in selecting and applying such tools. The objective of this work is to carry out a comparison and evaluation of objects that approach Cytology in Biology in high school. To achieve this goal, tools for dynamic learning will be selected. The results show that it is possible to use a main object and parallels to achieve the objective of the class. It is concluded that an object or a set can be used to better integrate the teaching-learning process..

Keywords: Learning Objects. Biology. Internet. Mobile devices.

1. Introduction

A The learning object or educational object is a resource in audio, video, image, etc. with the function of complementing what is taught in the classroom, and can be organized, adapted and reused according to the proposal in question (NICOLA, 2010) . The use of objects contributes to the change of learning in Biology in order to break the current limits of 2D figures, moving to 3D figures and animations, audios, among others. Often, the objects exist, they are already cataloged with their functions and instructions for use, however, the teacher does not know how to find, select which objects to use and how to apply them, making the use of such tools difficult.

The objective of this work is to carry out a comparison and evaluation of learning objects that address Cytology in Biology, focusing on 1st year high school students. To achieve this goal, the author selected the best tools that can improve student learning, seeking a better quality of classes in order to make them more dynamic.

As the main result found, it appears that teaching based on the use of educational objects in Cytology becomes pleasant, integrative and effective. Learning is done in a playful and dynamic way, in addition to reducing the costs of laboratories and tools for planning practical classes. Planning time costs are also reduced, as the content is pre-formatted for use, with the possibility of adaptation according to specific moments in the classes.

This work is structured in another 5 sections. In section 2 the Theoretical Framework is presented. Section 3 presents the methodology used. In section 4, the selection, evaluation and comparison of objects is carried out. In section 5, analyzes and discussions related to the results obtained are carried out. Finally, in section 6, the conclusions and perspectives for the continuation of this work are presented.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. At Information and Communication Technologies in Biology Teaching

Biology is the science that studies life in all its forms. The basis for studying life is the cell, the forming unit of living beings. (ALBERTS et al., 2006). Thus, it is essential for 1st year high school students to know the cell, the object of study of Cytology, even with the difficulties presented due to the complexity of the terms used and the difficulty of applying such knowledge in everyday life.

The teaching of Cytology, as pointed out by Reis et al. (2013), is carried out through the transmission of content, without the intertextuality, interdisciplinarity and relationship of problems with everyday situations, causing the student to become unmotivated and have learning difficulties. Lima (2009) reports that students learn through the decoration of the processes involved and two-dimensional drawings.

Garcia (2006) mentions that “information and communication technologies lead to new forms of mental activities, which affect the individual's way of acting and thinking”. Thus, the

school must be a social space for learning, combining ICTs with pleasurable learning, privileging all senses, such as sound, image, movement, animations (RUPPENTHAL et al., 2011), making students show themselves more satisfied and the effective teaching-learning process.

The use of innovative technologies in the classroom can guarantee the experience of participatory processes and teaching sharing in a dynamic process. However, this is not the reality in most schools (SILVA, 2003), as there are occasions when there is no computer or Internet connection, or even both. A solution for this case would be the use of mobile devices to eliminate the lack of equipment, enabling the development of active learning, open to suggestions and criticism from students.

Due to the constant use of new technologies by students, including in the school environment, using such resources as teaching tools makes classes more motivating, dynamic and fruitful (BASTOS, 2010), making these technologies become allies in the process of teaching-learning, in addition to contributing to learning about cells.

2.2. Learning Objects in Teaching Cytology in Biology

Nicola (2010) reports that the learning object is a tool that has the function of being a complement to what is learned in the classroom, and that it can be organized, adapted and reused according to the proposal in question. The use of these objects contributes so that formal and informal education are united, making learning more productive (GOMES, 2014).

The use of learning objects or educational objects in Biology classes has great benefits such as: motivation for knowledge and learning, acquired in a playful and dynamic way, and a reduction in the cost of laboratories and tools for planning practical classes. The reduction of planning time costs is also included, as the content is pre-formatted for use (NASCIMENTO, 2016).

However, according to Matta and Ribeiro (2012), many teachers are not aware of the existence of free learning objects. This fact may be related to little disclosure or insufficient training to handle such resources.

3. Methodology

To achieve the proposed objective, this work was divided into 5 sequential steps, shown in Figure 1, called Scope of Knowledge, Identification and Listing of Learning Objects, Selection of Objects, Comparative Evaluation and Analysis of Results.

Figure 1 - Work methodology flowchart

Source: Own authorship.

In the first step, Scope of Knowledge, the syllabus addressed in Cytology in the 1st year of high school will be listed, as well as highlighted figures and reported on how this content is taught today, considering at least three books used in public schools as reference .

The second stage, Identification and Listing of Learning Objects, consists of using search engines to find the main learning objects applicable in the teaching of Cytology. For this, keywords must be defined in order to find them. Then the found objects will have their names listed. Only tools that address one or more topics listed in the first step will be listed.

In the third step, **Selection of Objects**, a set of criteria will be established to define which objects identified in the second stage will in fact be analyzed and compared.

The fourth step, Comparative Evaluation, will be compared which educational objects are more suitable for the teaching-learning process. Will be compared which objects are more focused on the topic of Cytology and the level of education that will be applied.

The fifth stage, Analysis of Results, is represented by the analysis of student learning, in the possibility of learning objects to be used according to the choice of criteria described in the third stage. It will also be evaluated which objects have greater efficiency and pedagogical potential.

4. Development

This section contains the application of the methodology from the previous section.

4.1. Scope of Knowledge

The contents of Cytology in the discipline of Biology in the 1st year of high school throughout the school year, according to the Ministry of Education (MEC) are presented in table 1, which in turn is compared with the same contents covered in the State of Minas Gerais , according to the National Curriculum Parameters (PCN+).

Table 1 - Syllabus treated in Cytology in the 1st year of high school in Brazil

CONTENTS	TOPICS (CONTENT DETAILS)
optical instruments	Structure of different living beings and cell organization.
Different cell types	Organization and functioning of different types of cells.
single origin	Common characteristics among living things
cell interior	Golgiense complex, lysosomes, ribosomes, mitochondria. Centrioles, chloroplast, smooth and rough endoplasmic reticulum, Karyotheca, Nucleoplasm, chromatin and Nucleolus.
Basic vital functions and their related processes	Cell membrane. Energy acquisition processes by living systems – photosynthesis, cellular respiration. Cell reproduction and cancer. Hereditary material in cells of different types of organism. Cell cycle and its processes.

Source: BRAZIL, Ministry of Education – PCN+ (2005).

The Common Basic Content (CBC) of Biology adopted by the Secretary of State for Education of Minas Gerais is very similar to the contents of the National Curriculum Parameters, as shown in table 2.

Table 2 - Cytology syllabus in the 1st year of high school in Minas Gerais

CONTENTS	TOPICS (CONTENT DETAILS)
cell wraps	Cell theory. Cell wraps. Plasma membrane. Wraps outside the plasma membrane. Exchange processes between the cell and the external environment. Concentration of a solution.
cytoplasmic organelles	Golgi complex, lysosomes, ribosomes, mitochondria. Centrioles, chloroplast, smooth and rough endoplasmic reticulum.
Cell core	Karyotheca, Nucleoplasm and chromatin, Nucleolus.
cell division	Cell Cycle, Interphase, Mitosis and Meiosis in Animal Cells, Plant Cells, Prophase, Metaphase, Anaphase, Telophase and Cytokinesis, Mitosis in Plant Cells, Meiosis, Meiosis I, Meiosis II.
energy metabolism	Photosynthesis, Breathing, Fermentation, Chemosynthesis.

Source: Minas Gerais State Department of Education (2005).

Comparing the two tables, it is possible to notice that the contents are similar, but covered in depth in some subjects and more generally in others. Therefore, it can be said that the contents covered in the State of Minas Gerais are divided, according to the needs and reality of the target audience, and it is noticeable that the themes follow national guidelines and the textbooks themselves. This work, therefore, will adopt the contents used in Minas Gerais.

Biology textbooks used in public schools seek to demonstrate, with theory and some practices, the topics covered. However, despite covering all contents, they are little interconnected with technology and its main tools, making teaching theoretical and out of reality for students.

In the book “Biology” by César da Silva Junior, Sezar Sasson and Nelson Caldini Júnior, it has sections of activities, to develop the skills required in Enem related to Cytology. The program is complete, dosed in the right measure with language adequate to the level of the students, avoiding excessive technical terms.

The book “Biology – Volume Único”, by the same previous authors, offers a fluent and easy-to-understand textbook, establishing direct communication with the student, with complementary readings and exercises that lead the student to “think biologically”.

The book “Biology in Context” by José Mariano Amabis and Gilberto Rodrigues Martho, brings an interdisciplinary approach, relating aspects of scientific knowledge, practices of argumentative rationality and seeking approximations of Cytology with other fields of Science and other areas of knowledge, relating them with everyday life.

4.2. Identification and Listing of Learning Objects

The keywords used on the “Google” search engine are: “educational objects”; “learning objects”; "cytology"; "high school". The search for “cytology educational objects” leads to specific results, taking the user to a listing of objects. The search for “cytology learning objects” brings a listing of tutorials, manuals and articles on the application of the objects. In this search, it also indicates addresses of repositories with greater amounts of materials, which, according to the proposed research, are:

1. MERLOT – www.merlot.org/merlot
2. NOAS – www.noas.com.br
3. Teacher's Portal – portaldoprofessor.mec.gov.br
4. International Bank of Educational Objects – educational-objects2.mec.gov.br

The first 30 links of each of the repositories that lead to the educational objects sought were visited. Table 3 shows the list of learning objects found in each of the repositories.

Table 3 - List of learning objects and their repositories

ID	Official Learning Object Name	Repository
1	Protein Folding	NOAS
two	Hydrogen Bonds in Water Molecules	Teacher's Portal

3	mutations	International Bank of Educational Objects
4	Translation	International Bank of Educational Objects
5	Transcription	International Bank of Educational Objects
6	Protein Synthesis	Teacher's Portal
7	Diffusion through a Permeable Membrane	NOAS
8	Through a Semipermeable Membrane	NOAS
9	Diffusion & Molecular Mass	NOAS
10	Role of Temperature in Diffusion	Teacher's Portal
11	Diffusion of Dye in Water	International Bank of Educational Objects
12	Protein Synthesis and Secretion Experiment	MERLOT
13	Meselson-Stahl Experiment	International Bank of Educational Objects
14	Allele Variety	MERLOT
15	Evolution of Cell Organelles	Teacher's Portal
16	Mitosis	NOAS
17	Meiosis	NOAS
18	Cell Organelles	NOAS
19	Breathing	NOAS
20	Photosynthesis	NOAS
21	DNA transcription	NOAS
22	Membrane Channels	Teacher's Portal
23	Cell Model	MERLOT
24	Cells Alive	MERLOT
25	learning by osmosis	NOAS
26	Electron Transport Chain	NOAS
27	Apoptosis and Necrosis	Teacher's Portal

Source: Own authorship.

4.3. Selection of Objects

A preliminary selection was made with the criterion of choosing the first 30 objects of each repository, from these, those that exclusively address the theme “Cytology” were chosen, resulting in 27 objects. Seeking a dynamic and interactive teaching, educational objects aimed only at images, audio and/or videos were disregarded. Preference was given to complete objects, integrating animations and resources that facilitate knowledge, such as audios, videos and texts.

From the data analysis, a secondary selection was carried out, where learning objects were searched for in the repositories and excluding those that were not of interest. The remaining 27 were analyzed, following the following criteria: free license, language of use in Portuguese, be executable in mobile applications, and correctness.

The importance of the type of license criterion is due to the fact that the public school does not have enough resources to invest in technology, and it is necessary to use free learning objects.

As for the language criterion, objects were excluded entirely in English, and in intuitive English, those in which the images help their understanding and that do not present texts, but words or expressions similar to the Portuguese language. Thus, only objects in Portuguese were chosen to facilitate the students' understanding and the handling of resources.

The criterion that objects must run on mobile devices arose due to the lack of computer equipment in educational institutions. In cases of students without a smartphone or internet access, the possible solution is pairs of work, according to the availability of each student.

As for the correctness criterion, after verifications, it was observed that the veracity of the content is in conformity as well as the information is up to date, with no typing, spelling and grammar errors and other inconsistencies being found. All these evaluations of the objects were intended to verify the veracity of the content, as well as to identify whether the information is up to date.

The selection was made observing the importance of verifying reliable sources, in addition to paying attention to copyright, so that they are not violated. How many topics in the Cytology syllabus listed in the first step are covered by the learning object are considered.

4.4. Comparative Evaluation

The number of topics covered by the application and the application's suitability score for teaching Cytology based on the author's experience, followed by comparison, were adopted as comparative evaluation criteria. Only objects that present two or more topics on the menu were selected. In this way, for each application a grade will be given, based on the teaching experience regarding the most suitable object for the students and school grade of work.

The evaluation strategy was divided into two comparative analyses. In the first part, we analyzed the number of topics covered by the menu and the correct functionality of the system, as shown in table 4. In the second stage, the selected objects were compared according to the most worked out criteria.

Based on the subjects covered by each learning object, a mapping of the content and learning objects in which they meet certain content was carried out. In the first stage, 27 educational objects related to cytology were found. Of these, 19 are in English, 17 with an intuitive and easy-to-understand language, due to the rich illustrations and materials available; the other 2 present texts entirely in English, making it difficult to understand the object.

Quadro 4 - Mapeamento dos conteúdos e abordados pelos objetos de aprendizagem

Conteúdo	Identificação dos Objetos de Aprendizagem																										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
A teoria celular																			X				X				
Os envoltórios celulares	X														X				X				X				X
Membrana plasmática							X	X										X	X			X	X		X	X	X
Envoltórios externos a membrana plasmática	X	X																	X				X		X	X	X
Processos de troca entre a célula e o meio externo	X									X	X								X				X		X		X
Concentração de uma solução	X								X			X	X													X	
Complexo de Golgi																			X				X				
Lisossomos																			X				X	X			
Ribossomos	X																		X				X	X			
Mitocôndrias						X													X	X			X	X		X	
Centríolos																			X				X	X		X	
Cloroplasto																			X				X	X			
Reticulo endoplasmático liso e rugoso																			X				X	X			
Carioteca			X																X				X				
Nucleoplasma e cromatina	X		X	X															X				X	X			X
Núcleo			X																X				X	X			
Divisão celular e Ciclo celular			X	X	X	X								X		X	X					X					
Fotossíntese																					X			X			
Respiração e Fermentação																				X			X				
Quimiosíntese																							X				X
Quantidade de tópicos	6	1	4	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	11	7	1	1	1	18	8	4	4	6

Fonte: Autoria própria.

The objects "Protein Folding", "Mutations", "Translation" and "Transcription" have great educational quality, as well as the objects "Cell Model" and "Cells Alive" are quite rich and with great pedagogical potential, with more than two topics in Cytology. However, these 19 objects were discarded, including those cited due to the English language. The object "Membrane Channels" was discarded due to failures to run on mobile devices.

After selection, 7 educational objects made available in Portuguese were considered. The objects "Cell Organelles", "Respiration", "Photosynthesis" and "DNA Transcription" have a guide for support and help support. They are well-designed, illustrated, interactive, dynamic and very intuitive softwares, where the student can learn autonomously or with the help of the teacher. The objects "Learning by Osmosis", "Electron Transport Chain" and "Apoptosis and Necrosis" do not have instruction manuals, but present a friendly and easy-to-understand interface.

The 7 objects mentioned are more focused on the topic of Cytology and the level of applied teaching. The educational objects have all the requirements presented by the research, requiring refinement to choose the best one to be used during the course classes. The result of this refinement is shown in table 5, which represents the second stage of evaluation. This evaluation took place according to the notes released concerning the teacher's experience. The assessment grade scale ranges from 6 to 10 points. They are: 6 – weak, 7 – fair, 8 – good, 9 – great, 10 – excellent.

Table 5 - Evaluation of learning objects after refinement

object name	Strong points	Weaknesses	Note	Justification of use
Cell Organelles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Features an instruction manual; - Images that correspond to reality; - Determines the study interest points, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Covers only cell organelles; - Zooming images loses sharpness and digital quality. 	10	It can be used as a complement or even as a practical class, in the absence of a physical laboratory. High pedagogical quality to help with classroom activities.

Breathing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It has an interactive cycle and animation; - Well-designed tests for assessment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animation requires prior study for its visualization and understanding; - Has a certain degree of difficulty. 	8	Must be used in conjunction with the teacher. Although complex, it has rich content.
Photosynthesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It has an interactive cycle, animation and tests; - Allows you to learn unique plant cell themes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animation requires prior study of the topic; - Animation presents a lot of abstraction in the images. 	8	Must be used in conjunction with the teacher. Excellent for use in plant cell and photosynthesis classes.
DNA transcription	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animation very well elaborated and updated; - Provides student participation in the topic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires specific knowledge about DNA; - Need to complete a previous step to move forward; - Animation with abstractions. 	9	The software can be used in Cytology and Genetics classes. The student learns in practice the process of DNA transcription.
learning by osmosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perfect simulation of a laboratory; - Well explanatory and interactive content; - Processes represented, according to reality and rich in details. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to complete steps to follow up on the next ones; - Absence of user manual. 	10	It can be used as a complement or even as a practical class, in the absence of a physical laboratory. High pedagogical quality to help with classroom activities.
Electron Transport Chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well-designed and updated animation; - Well-represented processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animation requires prior study for its visualization and understanding; - It presents a certain degree of difficulty and complexity; 	8	It presents a degree of complexity, it must be used together with the teacher. The CTE scheme and its

		- Absence of user manual.		complexes are very well demonstrated.
Apoptosis and Necrosis	- Simulation of everyday life; - Well-designed and updated animation; - Well-represented processes.	- Absence of user manual.	9	It can be used as a complement or as a practical lesson and teaching aid in the classroom. It has rich educational content.

Source: Own authorship.

The object “Cell organelles” presents a laminar to observe images of the main cytoplasmic organelles, evidenced with the use of specific dyes, emphasizing the relationship between the quantity and distribution of organelles with the cell type shown. The photographs are under an optical microscope, with magnifications from 200x to 1000x, making it possible to explore rich details with the virtual microscope.

The “Learning by Osmosis” software demonstrates the osmosis process with related concepts: concentration gradient, osmotic pressure, plasmolysis, hemolysis, etc., in animal and plant cells, as well as its implications for the functioning of these organisms with the non-cell death process. programmed, necrosis in cells exposed to extreme temperature conditions and the relationship of this process of the extracellular matrix with the external environment.

As shown in table 5, it appears that the objects "Cellular organelles" covers 11 topics from the Cytology syllabus and "Learning by Osmosis" presents 6 topics and, according to their strengths and weaknesses, they obtained a score of 10.

5. Analysis of Results and Discussions

Learning objects must be attractive to students, so that they draw attention and arouse interest in the subject and its contents covered. The materials must primarily be free and entirely in Portuguese, with a friendly and easy-to-handle interface, in addition to the need to work on

mobile devices. For the material to fit these conditions, it must cover two or more categories of multimedia resources, such as sounds, images, videos and animations.

The object “Cell Organelles” is a good option for the teacher to conduct a practical class, simulating a cytology laboratory, providing students with a quality practical class. This class can be complemented with the “Respiration” object, which demonstrates cellular respiration, the process of obtaining energy from aerobic living beings. In specific cases, such as the differences between the apoptotic and necrotic processes can be explained with the help of the “Apoptosis and Necrosis” software, as well as the “Photosynthesis” object, which can be used to explain the plant cell.

After refinement and selection, the learning object for application in high school, "Cell organelles" and "Learning by Osmosis", are the ones that proved to be the most complete and most scored in the comparative assessment, within reality and with a language close to the students. These objects, like the others, should be used and adapted according to the teacher's preference and students' needs, given the importance of using other objects in parallel as teaching support.

6. Conclusions

The objective of this work was to carry out a comparison and evaluation of learning objects that address Cytology in Biology, focusing on 1st year high school students. After researching educational objects related to Cytology, 27 objects with a free use license and executable on mobile devices were found.

From the selection of objects in Portuguese, those that address a greater number of topics related to the subject were chosen, resulting in seven. The objects “Cell Organelles” and “Learning by Osmosis” proved to be efficient, as they work as simulators in the cytology laboratory. However, to eliminate the lack of practical exercises for fixing the contents worked, it is recommended to use other objects in parallel, as an aid in the teaching-learning process.

Learning objects have a playful and interactive character, enabling the motivation of students, in addition to contributing to the understanding of subjects discussed in class, becoming a facilitator in the teaching-learning process, in addition to making the student actively participate in the your learning. An educational object has great pedagogical potential, so it can be used together with another object to achieve the objective of a given class.

Knowing that this work does not intend to exhaust the subject and given the huge offer of free learning objects, further research is needed that seeks to select the tools according to the specific needs of each class, in addition to the proper practical application to compare what are the potential benefits of using these instruments.

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